

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Ethnobotany of medicinal plants used among the Bodo community living in urban localities of Kokrajhar district, BTAD region, Assam

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Abstract

Present study documented medicinal plants used by the Bodo community living in the urban areas of Kokrajhar district of BTAD, Assam. 20 villages of urban localities were visited randomly and 60 informants (27 male and 33 female) were interviewed using structured questionnaire format and focused group discussion. Study recorded a total of 104 medicinal plant species belonging to 94 genera and 56 families utilized for treatment of 30 ailments. Asteraceae was reported with the highest number of 8 species.

1. Introduction

Around 60,000 years ago, during the middle Paleolithic period, humans began using plants as medicine. Since then, they have learned to recognize and utilize plants based on their specific needs (Solecki and Shanidar, 1975). According to estimates, roughly 50,000 of the 4,22,000 plant species reported in the world are used medicinally while 43% of them are found in India (Govaerts, 2000; Schipmann et al., 2002). About 65% of people worldwide use plants as medicine for local healthcare, where ethnomedicinal knowledge play a crucial role (Pushpagandan, 1996). For the ethnic communities that live in India, ethnomedicine is crucial to their medical well-being. Since prehistoric times, several generations of people have learned about plants utilization through oral literature (Arora, 1987). People used plants as a kind of treatment before modern medicine was created. However, the preservation and continuation of traditional knowledge are at risk in present century due to passing away of the elderly generation (Anyinam, 1995). In India, around 7500 plant species are utilized in traditional medical procedures, and more than 2000 species of ethnomedicine and folk medicine have recently been discovered to produce drugs (Pushpagandan, 1995; Abhijit and De, 2010).

Assam, also known as the "land of red rivers and blue hills," is the entry point to Northeast India and is home to many indigenous tribal people that have long coexisted peacefully with the environment. A variety of races, including Mongolian, Indo-Burmese, Indo-Iranian, and Aryan, make up Assamese people (Borthakur, 1980). Of the 78,438 km² that make up Assam, 26,832 km² are classified forest land. Rich in flora and wildlife of ecological, economic, and cultural significance, BTAD is located in the foothills of the Great Himalayas and north bank of the Brahmaputra River (Endle 2011; CDPS 2004; Borthakur et al. 2018; Basumatary et al., 2023). Present ethnomedicinal study was conducted in the urban localities of the Kokrajhar Block of Kokrajhar District of BTAD region of Assam.

Study area: The four districts that make up BTAD are Udalguri, Chirang, Baksa, and Kokrajhar, and they span 9612 square kilometers in the northwest of Assam. With a total size of 3169.22 km², Kokrajhar (Figure 1) is the largest of the four districts. It is located at latitudes 26°46' and 27°77' North and longitudes 92°08' and 95°15' East. According to Yutika et al (2016), it is bordered by Bhutan in the North, Sonkosh River to the west, Cooch Bihar, and the West Bengal district of Jalpaiguri, and Brahmaputra valley and Chirang district to the south.

2. Materials and methods

Field survey, sample size, interview schedule and data collection: From the Kokrajhar block of Kokrajhar district of BTAD, covering a total of 60 informants (Table 1) (27 were male and 33 were female) interviewed from 21 urban villages (Table 2). A pre-structured questionnaire format developed in accordance with the methods suggested by Phillips et al (1994), Martin (1995), Tag (2007), and Tag et al (2012) was used during interviews with local informants. Village details, name, age, gender, and occupation of the informant; vernacular name of medicinal plants; parts of plant used; and method of preparation and administration of medicine against each ailment were recorded in the field notebook. The plant species were collected by transect walk with local herbalist, identified and gathered from their kitchen gardens and the surrounding environment. Voucher specimen was collected as per standard method suggested by Jain and Rao (1977) and Das (2021). Digital photographs were taken for each species using a CANON 1500D camera. Collected plants were identified in the laboratory using different floras including *Flora of British India* (Hooker 1872 – 1897), *Bengal Plants* (Prain, 1903), *Flora of Assam* (Kanjjilal et al., 1934 – 1940), and *Flora of BTAD* (Borthakur et al., 2018). In some cases, expert taxonomists were consulted and matched with images of specimens available online from different Herbaria. Plant names were updated mostly from <https://powo.science.kew.org/>. A set of voucher specimens has been deposited in the HAU (Herbarium at the Department of Botany), Rajiv Gandhi University, Arunachal Pradesh for future reference.

Figure 1. Map showing study site – Kokrajhar district and Kokrajhar block with urban villages visited for ethno-medico-botanical study.

Table 1. Demography and informants' ratio interviewed from Kokrajhar urban area.

Variable	Categories	No. of informants	Percentage
Gender	Male	27	45
	Female	33	55
Age group	35-50	40	66.66
	50-65	16	26.66
	Above 65	4	6.666
Occupation	Herbal practitioner	6	10
	House wife	29	48.33
	Farmer	21	35
	others	2	3.33

Table 2. Name of villages surveyed in Kokrajhar urban area

SN	Name of village
1	New Debargaon
2	New Thilapara
3	Hatugaon/sobaijhar
4	Suthar para
5	Swnab Dobinjora
6	Balajan tiniali
7	Bor batharbari
8	Lwkhwna bari
9	Janagaon
10	Onthao gwlaio
11	South Bismur
12	Dhonpur
13	Mainaopur
14	No.1 Bismuri
15	No.2 Ulta pani
16	Gwjwnphuri
17	Laal mati
18	Khusia kaati
19	Diajjjori
20	Balagaon

3.1. Demography and knowledge contribution

This study interviewed 60 informants (male 27, female 33) of which 26.66% are belonging to the age group 50 – 65 while 66.66% informants belonging to the age group between 35-50 and only 6.65% informants belonging to age group 65 years and above. Only 10% of the total informants are reported to be herbal practitioners while 48.33% is housewife, 35% is farmer and rest 3.33% informants belonging to other categories which together contributes to the sharing of ethnomedicinal plant information recorded from 20 villages of Kokrajhar area (Table 1 and 2) of BTAD region. Early informants (50 years above) were observed to be more knowledgeable in medicinal plant identification and management than the younger age group informants.

3.2. Taxonomic diversity of medicinal plant taxa and families

The present study recorded the use of 104 medicinal plants belonging to 94 genera and 56 families (Table 3). Of all the families (Figure 1), Asteraceae has been reported with the highest number of 8 species which was followed by Lamiaceae with 7 families, Apocynaceae, Fabaceae, and Zingiberaceae with 5 species each. Solanaceae with 4 species, Combretaceae, Malvaceae, and Poaceae with 3 species each. Acanthaceae, Amaranthaceae, Amyrilidaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Moraceae, Rubiaceae, Urticaceae, and Malvaceae with 2 species each and the rest with 1 species each. Growth habit of the plants is presented in Figure 2 which showed that majority of the species reported are herbs (44.81%) which is followed by shrubs and trees (18.83% each), climber (12.99%), aquatic herb (3.90%) while few tree species were found to be harvested and used (0.65%).

3.3. Plant part harvested, mode of herbal formulation and application

Most of the parts used (Figure 3) for the medicinal plants are leaves (35 spp.) which is followed by fruits (12 spp.), roots and twigs (11 spp.) each, whole plant (8 spp.), bark (7 spp.), flowers (5 spp.), rhizome and seeds (4 spp.) each, branch with (3 spp.), stem and tuber (2 spp.) each and remaining with 1 spp. each. This study documents 51 species to

be used as paste followed by 19 spp. as extract, 12 spp. as decoction, 11 spp. as pieces, 7 spp. as globules/pills, 6 spp. as juice and powder each, 2 spp. as cooked, juice extract, roast each and 1 spp. as brush.

3.4. Ailment categories and medicinal plant utilization

Present study has recorded 30 ailments categories recorded from the study sites wherein several medicinal plants are employed for their treatment (Table 3). 11 species were used in bone fracture, 13 spp. in cuts followed by 10 spp. each in and stomach ache, which is again followed by 9 spp. in gastric and allergy, 7 spp. for toothache, 6 spp. for headache and nose bleeding, 5 spp. each for piles and wound, 4 spp. for colic, and typhoid, 3 spp. each for Urinary Tract Infection (UTI), digestion, and chicken pox. 2 spp. each for boil, kidney stone, mouth ulcer and fever. 1 species each for lower abdomen pain, blemish, High blood pressure, cancerous wound, tooth cavity, cough, diabetes, diarrhea, eye problem, hiccups, lactation, snake bite, dysentery, and migraine. There is repetitive use of same plant in different ailments. Among all of the plants recorded, 41.34% of the plants are reported to be harvested from the wild such as *Achyranthes aspera*, *Acmella paniculata*, *Ageratum conyzoides*, *Alstonia scholaris*, *Aristolochia assamica*, *Aristolochia indica*, *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Centella asiatica*, *Chromolaena odorata*, *Clerodendrum indicum*, *Clerodendrum infortunatum*, *Crassocephalum crepidioides*, *Cyclea peltata*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Dendrocnide sinuata*, *Eclipta prostrata*, *Equisetum ramosissimum* var. *huegeli*, *Phallus indusiatus*, *Flueggea leucopyrus*, *Garcinia pedunculata*, *Gonostegia hirta*, *Hemidesmus indicus*, *Hydrocotyle sibthorpioides*, *Hypericum japonicum*, *Leucas aspera*, *Bonnaya antipoda*, *Mikania micrantha*, *Mimosa pudica*, *Paederia foetida*, *Persicaria hydropiper*, *Plumbago zeylanica*, *Rauwolfia serpentina*, *Saccharum spontaneum*, *Scoparia dulcis*, *Senna occidentalis*, *Solanum torvum*, *Solanum viarum*, *Stellaria wallichiana*, *Stephania rotunda*, *Streblus asper*, and *Thelypteris parasitica*. 50% of the species reported are found cultivated such as *Ricinus communis*, *Alternanthera brasiliana*, *Ananas comosus*, *Andrographis paniculata*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Bambusa bambos*, *Bassella alba*, etc. 7.69% of so many were found sold in the market like, *Syzygium aromaticum*, *Myristica fragrans*, *Holarrhena antidysenterica*, *Elwendia persica*, *Elettaria cardamomum*, *Cinnamomum tamala*, *Borassus flabellifer*, and *Amomum subulatum*. These spices are mostly used in traditional medicine preparation.

Corroboration with available literature shows that Bodo community of Kokrajhar district are reported to be rich in traditional knowledge related to utilization of different parts of medicinal plants since early days (Twinkle et al., 2024). Roots and rhizomes were reported to be widely used by the Bodo community of Kokrajhar district while 23 species were found to be used for the treatment of diabetes (Sarmah et al., 2021). Swargiary et al (2021) also reported on putative anthelmintic plants used in traditional medicine system of Kokrajhar district. Daimari and Manita (2019) reported antidiabetic medicinal plants used by the Bodo tribe of Kokrajhar. Basumatary et al (2023) also reported 31 medicinal plant species used for the treatment of stomach disorders in BTAD region. Plants such as *Azadirachta indica*, *Paederia foetida*, *Ocimum tenuiflorum*, *Mimosa pudica*, *Mikania micrantha*, *Mangifera indica*, *Hypericum japonicum*, *Hydrocotyle sibthorpioides*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Clerodendrum infortunatum*, and *Centella asiatica* are found to be used in highest numbers. *Centella asiatica* is reported to be in use against numerous ailments like blood purifier, appetizer, and also used for the

treatment of diarrhea, leprosy, tuberculosis, amoebiasis (Kirtikar and Basu, 1935; Yakang et al., 2013; Chandrika and Kumarab, 2015; Ünü, 2022). *Clerodendrum infortunatum* reported as antimicrobial agent (Ashish et al., 2010), antihelmintic (Ashish et al., 2010b), hepatoprotective (Shantanu et al., 2009) anticonvulsant (Shantanu et al., 2009), wound healing (Gouthamchandra et al., 2009), analgesic (Shantanu et al., 2009), and antioxidant activities (Modi et al., 2010; Bhattacharjee et al., 2011). The *Ocimum tenuiflorum* has also been suggested to possess antifertility, anticancer, antidiabetic, antifungal, antimicrobial, cardioprotective, analgesic, antispasmodic and adaptogenic actions. Pattanayak et al (2010) also reported *Mimosa pudica* against leprosy, dysentery, vaginal and uterine complaints, and inflammations, burning sensation, asthma, leucoderma, fatigue and blood diseases (Joseph et al., 2013).

4. Conclusion

Present study reported good number of important medicinal plant species used by the residents of urban localities of the Kokrajhar district of BTAD, Assam. Despite of availability of modern health care facilities in urban area, local residents still rely on the treatment methods of traditional healers for certain ailments. This reflects the popularity and efficacy of the traditional medicinal plants used by the healers of Bodo community. However, the number of conventional traditional medical practitioners and procedures are dwindling due to death of the experience herbalists. Advanced chromatographic and clinical pharmacological methods should be employed to validate potential phytocompounds from selected medicinal plants reported against various ailments.

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Authors' contributions

The first author (JB) generated the field data and prepared the draft manuscript. The second and the third authors (PHK and HT) are PhD supervisors and mentors who formulated the research design and contributed in intellectual approach, and critically reviewed and finalized the draft manuscript.

Declaration of conflict of interest

Authors have no conflict of interest.

Table 3. Checklist of ethnomedicinal plants used by the Bodo community living in the urban localities of Kokrajhar district, BTAD, Assam.

SN	Biological name	Vernacular name	Pars used	Uses	Habit	Crude drug type	Preparation
1	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L. [Amaranthaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-016 (HAU), 21.02.2022.	Sampher ultha	Roots	Tooth ache	Herb	Piece	A piece of root is insert in the cavity of the tooth during toothache.
2	<i>Acmella paniculata</i> (Wall.ex DC.) [Asteraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 072 (HAU), 23.03.2022	Usumwi	Twigs	Jaundice	Herb	Paste	Ground together into paste which is then turn into tiny globules which after sundried for 3-4 days can be consume after the meal.
3	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L. [Asteraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 131 (HAU), 23.11.2022.	Mwnam dari/ Khal met	Twigs	Cuts	Herb	Paste	Leaves are crushed and the paste applied on the cut area to stop the bleeding.
4	<i>Allium sativum</i> L. [Amaryllidaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 096 (HAU), 07.04.2022	Sambram gufur	Bulb	Fever and nose bleeding	Herb	Tempering and paste	1. Fever: Cloves are tampered with the help of Mustard oil and rub on the forehead, palm and back. 2. Nose bleeding: Cloves are ground along with mustard oil and eat with the hot rice.
5	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R.Br. [Apocynaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 138 (HAU), 23.11.2022.	Omakhi bilai/Sithaona	Leaves and Bark	Wound and Gastric	Tree	Paste and Juice extract	1. Wound: Ground together and applied on the wound. 2. Gastric: Ground altogether into paste along with black salt and soaked in the water the whole night and extract is to drink empty stomach.
6	<i>Alternanthera brasiliiana</i> (L.) Kuntze [Amaranthaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 301 (HAU), 12.11.22	Phool gwja	whole plant	Stop bleeding	Herb	Paste	Leaves are grinded into paste and is applied on the freshly cut wound
7	<i>Amomum subulatum</i> Roxb. [Zingiberaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-021 (HAU), 25.02.2022.	Boro elasi	Seeds	Headache	Herb	Paste	Grinded with few drops of water into paste and is applied on the head for 5-6 hours.
8	<i>Ananas comosus</i> (L.) Merr. [Bromeliaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 121 (HAU), 23.10.2022	Anaros bilai	Leaves	Hiccups	Herb	Extract	Leaves are grinded and then the juice extract is taken to cure hiccups.
9	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Nees. [Acanthaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 132 (HAU), 23.11.2022	Siruta gwkha	Leaves	Stomachache	Herb	Globules, extract	1. Stomachache: Leaves are grinded into paste and turn into tiny globules which can be consumed. 2. Leaves are grinded and the juice extract is taken.
10	<i>Aristolochia assamica</i> D.Borah & T.V.Do [Aristolochiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 137 (HAU), 23.11.2022	Nilikhor	Roots	Stomach ache	Climber	Extract	Roots are grinded and the juice extract is consumed to heal stomach ache.
11	<i>Aristolochia indica</i> L. [Aristolochiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 302 (HAU), 12.11.22	Nilikhor	Roots	Snake bite	Climber	Extract, Paste	Roots are grinded and the juice extract is consumed and abstain from drinking water for some hours.
12	<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i> L. [Asteraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 303 (HAU), 13.11.22	Na deona	Leaves	Blood pressure	Shrub	Paste	Grinded with rice and applied on the forehead.
13	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss. [Meliaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-256 (HAU), 12.12.2022	Neem	Leaves	Allergy, cuts and wounds. and Chicken pox	Small tree	Decoction, Paste and Powder	1. Allergy: Boiled and let it cool down for some time after adding some lemon juice and apply against allergy. Boiled and the decoction of the leaves is used to take bath during allergy. 2. Cuts and Wound: Grinded to paste and apply 3. Chicken pox: <i>Flueqya leucopyrus</i> (leaves) fried along with other ingredient and are crushed and powder is applied on the chicken pox.
14	<i>Bambusa bambos</i> (L.) Voss [Poaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 303 (HAU), 13.11.22	Owa	Outer cover of the shoot	Cuts	Shrub	Powder	Outer part of the bamboo shoot is macerated into a powder and applied on the freshly cut wounds to stop bleeding.
15	<i>Basella alba</i> L. var rubra (L)Stewart [Basellaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 063 (HAU); 22.03.2022	Mwifrai	Twig	Wound (Like cancer)	Climber		Grinded and paste is applied on the wound.
16	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L. [Arecaceae]; Kokrajhar: Bor Bathabari, JB & HT- 142 (HAU), 02.02.2023.	Taal misri	Processed	Urine infection/body pain	Tree	Extract	Grinded into paste and liquid extract is consumed.
17	<i>Cajanus kerstingii</i> Harms [Fabaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 304 (HAU), 13.11.22	Kokhling	Leaves	Mouth ulcer	Shrub	Paste	Leaves are grinded with teeth into paste and apply on the ulcer
18	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) W.T.Aiton [Apocynaceae] Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 305 (HAU), 13.11.22	Gogonda bilai/Naru	Leaves	bone fracture/ Dislocation	Shrub	Paste	1. Bone fracture/dislocation: Finely grinded paste is applied on the fracture area and tied with the help of bandage and change every after 3-4 days. 2. Grinded into paste and wrapped with <i>Musa</i> leaves around the fractured area till recovery.
19	<i>Capsicum annum</i> L. [Solanaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-010 (HAU), 07.02.2022	Phanlu bwddwn	Fruit	Migraine	herb	Globules	Parts are ground into paste along with <i>Allium cepa</i> and Clove, Spider skin cover and formulated into small balls and then sundry it for some time and drink.
20	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) Urb. [Araliaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 001 (HAU), 02.02.2022.	Mani muni	Whole plant	Gastric, Jaundice, Colic (Babies cry), Piles, Typhoid	Herb	Paste, Decoction.	1. Gastric: Grinded into paste and soaked in to water for whole night and extract is to drink in empty stomach. 2. Jaundice: Cut into pieces along with the wings of the yellow bird and enter inside the cocoon.

							3. Colic: Boiled together in water, milk is added and then it is for used for bathing the kids. 4. Piles: Boiled and the decoction is drink after food. 5. Typhoid: Crushed into paste and put on the head of the patient until it cools down and sprinkle it with water whenever it dries.
21	<i>Corchorus capsularis</i> L. [Malvaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 106 (HAU), 09.10.2022	fatw	bark and stem	Cuts	shrub	Paste	Leaves are grinded into paste and apply on the freshly cut wound.
22	<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> (L.) R.M.King & H.Rob. [Asteraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 306 (HAU), 13.11.22	Lewa bendwng	Leaves	Bleeding stop	Shrub	Extract	Leaves are grinded and the paste extract is used for the treatment of bleeding.
23	<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i> (Bunch-Ham.) T.Nees & C.H.Eberm. [Lauraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 307 (HAU), 13.11.22	Tej pat	Leaves	Eye problem	Tree	Extract	2 pieces of leaves with 10 ml water, apply two drops in each eye 3 times in a month.
24	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> L. [Vitaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 116 (HAU), 11.11.2022	Hat zora	Stem and leaves	bone fracture/ Dislocation	Climber	Paste	Grinded along with into paste and wrapped after covering it with <i>Musa</i> leaves around the fractured area till recovery
25	<i>Citrus × limon</i> (L.) Osbeck [Rutaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 124 (HAU), 23.11.2022	Nareng Libu	Twigs and fruits	stomach ache and Gastric	Shrub	Juice extract and Roast	1. Stomach ache: Leaves are grinded into paste and turn into tiny globules which can be consumed. 2. Gastric: Fruit juice is used to drink in empty to cure stomach ache
26	<i>Citrus × aurantium</i> f. <i>aurantium</i> [Rutaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 308 (HAU), 13.11.22	Nareng komla bigur	Fruit peel	cancerous wound (putting)	Shrub	Paste	Grinded into paste and applied on the wound.
27	<i>Clerodendrum colebrookeanum</i> Walp. [Lamiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 007 (HAU), 03.02.2022	Mwkhwna bijou	Leaves	Lower abdomen pain and Stomach ache	Shrub	Globules	1. Lower abdomen: Leaves are grinded into paste along with <i>Psidium quajava</i> (leaves) and make into tiny balls and consumed. 2. Stomach ache: Leaves are grinded and juice extract is consumed.
28	<i>Clerodendrum indicum</i> (L.) Kuntze [Lamiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 103 (HAU), 09.10.2022.	Ekhla bir	Leaves	Leg and hand bone fracture	Shrub	Paste	Leaves are grinded into paste and is applied on the fracture area and tied with the help of bandage and change every after 3-4 days.
29	<i>Clerodendrum infortunatum</i> L. [Lamiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 271 (HAU), 17.04.2024	Mwkhwna	Twigs	Stomach ache. Gastric and Jaundice	Shrub	Globules	1. Stomach ache: Grinded into paste and the paste is turn into tiny pills which is then sun dried for some days and eat. 2. Gastric: parts are grinded into paste and soaked in the water for whole night and extract is taken in empty stomach. 3. Jaundice: Grinded into paste and the paste is turn into tiny pills which is then sun dried for some days and eat.
30	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L. [Fabaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 159 (HAU), 27.11.2022	Aparajita	Flowers	Digestion	Climber	Dry	Flowers dried are good for digestion.
31	<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L. [Arecaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 135 (HAU), 23.11.2022	Naringkhol bidwi	Coconut water	Kidney stone	Tree	Extract	Coconut water along with <i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> (Leaves) and taal is used to grind and the extract is taken.
32	<i>Crassocephalum crepidioides</i> (Benth.) S.Moore; [Asteraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 309 (HAU), 13.11.22	Doula	Leaves	Allergy	Herb	Paste	Leaves long with <i>Ricinus comunis</i> (young leaves) are ground into paste and applied on the skin.
33	<i>Crinum defixum</i> Ker Gawl. [Amyrilidaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 295 (HAU), 17.04.2024	Khanari	Leaves	Leg and hand bone fracture	Herb	Paste	Grinded into paste and apply on the fracture area and tied with the help of bandage, and change every after 3-4 days.
34	<i>Curcuma caesis</i> Roxb. [Zingiberaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-020 (HAU), 25.02.2022.	Khatri gswm	Rhizome	Stomach ache	Herb	Extract	Rhizome are grinded and the extract is taken during stomach ache.
35	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L. [Zingiberaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 296 (HAU), 27.04.2024	Haldwi gwhang	Rhizome	Gastric and Bone fracture	Herb	Extract	1. Gastric: Grinded into paste along with black salt and soaked in the water for the whole night and extract is taken during empty stomach. 2. Bone fracture: Rhizome along with <i>Tamarindus indica</i> (leaves), are grinded along with mustard oil and the paste is applied on the fractured area and wrapped for 3-4 days till recovery.
36	<i>Cyclea peltata</i> (Burm.f.) Hook.f. & Thomson; [Menispermaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 310 (HAU), 13.11.22	phennel khuga	Leaves/Vine	Jaundice	Climber	Paste Pieces	1. Leaves are grinded with water and put on the head side of the bed by taking his/her name. If there is jaundice then grinded paste will be thick. 2. Leaves are removed from the vines and the vines are bounded on both wrist and ankles.
37	<i>Cynodon dactylo</i> (L.) Pers. [Poaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 122 (HAU), 23.10.2022.	Dhuburi hagra	Whole plant	Allergy, dysentery, cuts, Bone fracture	Herb	Decoction, Juice, paste	1. Allergy: whole plant is boiled; let it cool down for some time and add lemon juice in the boiled extract. 2. Dysentery and Cuts: Crush and the extract is consumed for dysentery and applied on freshly cut wound. 3. Cuts: Grinded into paste and apply on the freshly cut wound.

							4. Bone fracture: parts are grinded into paste and bind on the broken with band aids and with bamboo sticks for support.
38	<i>Delonix regia</i> (Bojer ex Hook.) Raf. [Fabaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 311 (HAU), 13.11.22	Krishna sura bilai	Leaves	Tooth ache	Tree	Paste	Leaves are grinded into paste and the paste is applied on the tooth.
39	<i>Dendrocnide sinuata</i> (Blume) Chew; [Urticaceae]; Udalguri: JB & HT 061 (HAU), 22.02.2022	Khoma	Roots	Nose bleeding	Shrub	Extract	Roots are grinded with other ingredients and along with mustard oil which is taken along with hot rice.
40	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L. [Asteraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 312 (HAU), 13.11.22	Daogang jwla	Leaves	Blemish, Cuts and wound,	Herb	Ash of the paste, paste	1. Blemish: leaves are burned to ash and the ash is used along with oil and apply on blemish. 2. Cuts and wound: Leaves are burned to ash, mix with oil and apply in wound.
41	<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i> (L.) Maton; [Zingiberaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-035 (HAU), 05.03.2022.	Choto elasi	Seeds	Headache	Herb	Paste	Seeds are grinded with few ml of water into paste and apply on the head for 5-6 hours.
42	<i>Ehwendia persica</i> (Boiss.) Pimenov & Kljuykov; [Apiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 313 (HAU), 13.11.22	kala jeera	Seeds	Fever, headache	Herb	Decoction	1. Fever: Seeds are boiled with mustard oil and apply on the nose, palm etc. 2. Headache: Seeds are grinded with few ml of water into paste and apply on the head for 5-6 hours.
43	<i>Equisetum ramosissimum</i> var. <i>huegelii</i> (Milde) Christenh. & Husby; [Equisitaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 297 (HAU), 20.04.2024	nul jora	leaves	Bone fracture	Herb	Paste	Grinded into paste and put on the fractured area and tied with the help of bandage and change every after 34 days.
44	<i>Phallus indusiatus</i> Vent.; [Phallaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 313 (HAU), 13.11.22	Mwikhun je	Fruiting body	Wound (Like cancer)	Herb	Paste	Grinded to paste and applied on the wound.
45	<i>Flueggea leucopyrus</i> Willd. [Phyllanthaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 314 (HAU), 13.11.22	Huken	Leaves	Chicken pox	Shrub	Powder	Leaves are fried, crushed and applied on the chicken pox.
46	<i>Garcinia pedunculata</i> Roxb. ex Buch.-Ham.; [Clusiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 161 (HAU), 27.11.2022	Thaika	Fruit	Mild Jaundice	Tree	Dried	Fruits are cut into pieces and sundried for 3 days which is then eaten during mild jaundice.
47	<i>Gonostegia hirta</i> (Blume) Miq. [Urticaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 276(HAU), 17.04.2024	Samo laothi	Leaves	Wound (Like cancer)	Herb	Paste	Grinded to paste and applied on the wound.
48	<i>Hellenia speciosa</i> (J. Koenig) S.R.Dutta. [Costaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 315 (HAU), 13.11.22	Buri thokon	Rhizome	Burning urine	Shrub	Extract	Grinded into paste and extract is taken.
49	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) R.Br. [Apocynaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 077 (HAU), 12.03.2022	Bala Mwikhi	Twigs	Lactation	Herb	Cooked	Twigs are cooked and fed to the mother post-delivery of the child.
50	<i>Hibiscus × rosa-sinensis</i> L. [Malvaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 316 (HAU), 13.11.22	Joba phool	Flowers	Allergy	Small tree	Paste	Flowers are crushed into paste and apply on the skin.
51	<i>Holarhena antidysenterica</i> Wall. [Apocynaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 140 (HAU), 02.02.2023.	Indra job	Flowers (baught from the market)	Stomach ache	Small tree	Globule	Grinded into paste and turn into tiny globules and is sundried for some days and then consumed.
52	<i>Hydrocotyle sibthorpioides</i> Lam; [Araliaceae]; Udalguri: JB & HT-039 (HAU), 09.03.2022.	Mana Muni pisa	Whole plant	Jaundice, piles, colic (babies cry)	Herb	Paste, globules, and decoction	1. Jaundice: Grinded into paste and turn into a tiny globule which then is dried and eaten. 2. Piles: Grinded into paste and turn into a tiny globule which is then is dried and eaten for piles. 3. Colic: Boiled and the decoction is use for bathing the kid to cure colic.
53	<i>Hypericum japonicum</i> Thunb. Ex Murr; [Hypericaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 146 (HAU), 02.02.2023	Sona phuli	Whole plant	Typhoid, Jaundice, Gastric, and colic (babies cry)	Herb	Paste, extract, and decoction,	1. Typhoid: crushed into paste and apply on the head of the patient until it cools down and sprinkle it with water whenever it dries. 2. Jaundice: Grinded into paste and turn into a tiny globule which then is dried and eaten. 3. Gastric: Grinded into paste and soaked in the water for whole night and the extract is taken. 4. Colic (babies cry): Decoction is used for bathing the baby.
54	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L. [Euphorbiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 317(HAU), 13.11.22	Enda	Branch	Cavity	Shrub	As a brush	Stem is used as a brush.
55	<i>Justicia gendarussa</i> Macre ex Nees. [Acanthaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 318 (HAU), 13.11.22	Jatrashi	Leaves and branch	Colic (Babies cry) and Toothache	Herb	Decoction and as a whole.	1. Colic (Babies cry): Boiled with the water after the addition of water and used for bathing the babies. 2. Toothache: Stem is used as a brush to clean the teeth.
56	<i>Kalanchoe pinnata</i> (Lam.) Pers. [Crussalaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 299 (HAU), 20.04.2024	Paat gaja	Leaves	Kidney stone, burning urine.	Herb	Extract	1. Kidney stone: Grinded along with coconut juice and taal and the juice is drink in the morning in empty stomach. 2. Urine infection: Leaves are grinded and soaked for the whole night and the juice is consumed.

57	<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.) Link [Lamiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 49 (HAU), 20.03.2022	Khansisa	Leaves	Cuts and nose bleeding	Herb	Extract	1. Cuts: Leaves are grinded and the paste extract is used for the treatment of bleeding. 2. Nose bleeding: leaves are grinded into paste and the extract is applied on the nose bleeding.
58	<i>Bonnaya antipoda</i> (L.) Druce; [Linderniaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 319 (HAU), 13.11.22	Na bikhi	whole plant	Allergy	Herb	Paste	Grinded into paste and apply on the skin.
59	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L. [Anacardiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 043 (HAU), 09.04.2022.	Thajjou	Bark	Jaundice (Wearing), pressure like, Allergy, and stomach ache	Tree	Pieces, extract and decoction	1. Jaundice (Wearing): Barks are cut into pieces and put inside the cocoon of silkworm and wear it for 3-4 days. 2. High blood Pressure: grinded into paste along with some rice and applied on forehead. 3. Allergy: boiled the leaves and let it cool for some time and add lemon juice in the boiled extract. 4. Stomach ache: Bark of the stem are grinded along with <i>Senna occidentalis</i> leaves and extract is consumed during stomach ache.
60	<i>Maranta arundinacea</i> L.; [Maranthaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 278 (HAU), 17.04.2024	Bon chini or chop chini	Rhizome	Burning urine and stomach ache	Shrub	Extract	1. Burning urine: Rhizomes are grinded into paste and extract is taken. 2. Stomach ache: Rhizomes are grinded along with the rhizome of <i>Senna occidentalis</i> (leaves) and the extract is then consumed during severe stomach ache.
61	<i>Mentha piperita</i> L. [Lamiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 320 (HAU), 13.11.22	Pepper mint	Leaves	Headache	Herb	Paste	Grinded with few ml of water into paste and apply on the head for 5-6 hours.
62	<i>Mikania micrantha</i> Kunth [Asteraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 214 (HAU), 15.10.2023	Rifujee bendwng, latha bendwng	Twigs	Stop bleeding, Jaundice and stomach ache	Climber	Paste,	1. Stop bleeding: Leaves are grinded and the paste extract is used for the treatment of bleeding. 2. Jaundice: Crushed into paste along with other ingredients and put on the head of the patient until it cools down and sprinkle it with water whenever it dries 3. Stomach ache: Grinded into paste and turn into tiny balls and is sundried for some days and consumed.
63	<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L. [Mimosaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 123 (HAU), 23.11.2022	Daosa mwkreb	Whole plant and roots	Bone dislocation, Cuts and wound, Mild jaundice, blood pressure and cavity	Herb	Paste and pieces.	1. Bone dislocation: Whole plant is grinded into paste and bind it with bandage for whole six days in a month. 2. Cuts and wound: whole plant are grinded into paste and applied on the wound. 3. Mild jaundice: Parts are grinded into paste along with some rice and applied it on forehead. 4. Cavity: A piece of root is inserted into the cavity of the tooth during toothache.
64	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L. [Cucurbitaceae] Kokrajhar: JB & HT 164 (HAU), 03.12.2022	Fwrla gwkha	Fruits	Boil	Climber	Paste	Fruits are grinded into paste and applied on the boil.
65	<i>Morinda angustifolia</i> Roxb. [Rubiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-018 (HAU), 10.03.2022.	Aso gwkha	Roots	Mild Jaundice	Small tree	Pieces	Roots facing east are cut into pieces and put inside the cocoon and wear it for 3-4 days.
66	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam. [Moringaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 067 (HAU), 23.03.2023.	Swrjina,/sojona	Leaves and bark	Bone fracture and nose bleeding	Tree	Paste	1. Bone fracture: Leaves are grinded into paste and the paste is applied on the broken part and wrapped and bind with the band aids for some days. 2. Barks are grinded with along with mustard oil and taken along with hot rice.
67	<i>Morus alba</i> L. [Moraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 42 (HAU), 23.03.2022	Gongger thaisib	Roots	Jaundice	Tree	Pieces	Roots facing towards east are cut into pieces and put inside the cocoon and wear it for 3-4 days.
68	<i>Musa balbisiana</i> Colla [Musaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 36 (HAU), 08.04.2022	Athia thalir	Roots	Piles and Cavity	Tree	Paste	Decayed roots are grinded by taking the name of the patient and worms are supposed to come out of the roots.
69	<i>Myristica fragrans</i> Houtt. [Myristicaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-037 (HAU), 08.04.2022;	Joy phol	Fruits	Head ache	Tree	paste	Fruits are grinded with little water into Paste and apply on the head for 5-6 hours.
70	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> L. [Solanaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 139 (HAU), 23.11.2022.	Thanku	Dries leaves	Toothache	Shrub	Paste	Dry leaves are applied on the tooth.
71	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i> L. [Nyctentheaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 081 (HAU), 26.02.2022	Sewali	Flowers	Headache.	Small tree	Cooked	Flowers are cooked and consumed to heal jaundice, diabetes and malaria.
72	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> L. [Lamiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-045 (HAU), 09.03.2022.	Tulshi	Leaves	Jaundice, typhoid, fever and Colic (Babies cry)	Shrub	Paste and Extract	1. Jaundice and typhoid: Crushed into paste along with other ingredients and put on the head of the patient until it is cool down and sprinkle it with water whenever it dries. 2. Cough: Leaves along with honey and ginger tuber are grinded and juice extract is drink to cure. 3. Fever: Leaves are boiled with mustard oil and apply on the nose, palm etc.

							4. Colic (Babies cry): All the other ingredients are boiled together in water and milk is added which is used for bathing the baby.
73	<i>Oroxylum indicum</i> (L.) Vent. [Bignoniaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 013 (HAU), 14.02.2022	Kharokhandai	Stem and bark	Jaundice	Tree	Decoction	Bark of the tree is cleaned and the inner stem is cut into pieces and soaked in the water for whole night next day the extract is consumed.
74	<i>Paederia foetida</i> L. [Rubiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 055 (HAU), 20.03.2022	Khipi bendwng	Leaves and Twigs	Colic (babies cry) and Jaundice	Shrub	Decoction	1. Colic (Babies cry): Leaves are boiled together in water and milk is added and used for bathing the baby. 2. Jaundice: Grinded into paste and soaked in the water for whole night and the extract is used.
75	<i>Pandanus odorifer</i> (Forssk.) Kuntze [Pandaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 321 (HAU), 13.11.22	Khewa	Leaves	piles	Shrub	Globules	Leaves are grinded into paste which is then turn into tiny globules which then is sundried for some days and consumed.
76	<i>Persicaria hydropiper</i> (L.) Delarbre [Polygonaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 071 (HAU), 22.03.2022	Desongali	Leaves	Typhoid	Shrub	Paste	Crushed into paste and put on the head of the patient until it is cool down and sprinkle it with water whenever it dries.
78	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L. [Phyllanthaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-150 (HAU), 02.02.2023	Amblai	Fruits	Gastric	Tree	Decoction	Fruits are dried and grinded into powder and consumed during gastric.
79	<i>Piper longum</i> L. [Piperaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-033 (HAU), 03.03.2022.	Simpri	Fruits	Headache	Climber	Paste	Grinded with few ml of water into paste and apply on the head for 5-6 hours.
80	<i>Piper nigrum</i> L. [Piperaceae]; Kokrajhar JB & HT-028 (HAU), 02.03.2022.	Gol moris	Fruits	Nose bleeding	Climber	Paste	Fruits are grinded along with mustard oil and taken along with hot rice.
81	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L. [Plumbaginaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-017 (HAU), 21.03.2022.	Agwr sita	Roots	Jaundice	Herb	Pieces	Roots (facing) are cut into pieces and put inside the cocoon of silkworm and wear it for 3-4 days.
82	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L. [Myrtaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 133 (HAU), 11.02.2022	Sophari bijou/Swmptram bijou	Twigs	Stomach ache, and Gastric	Tree	Paste	1. Stomach ache: Leaves are grinded into paste along with <i>Clerodendum glandulosum</i> leaves and <i>Andrograpis peniculata</i> and juice extract is consumed. 2. Gastric: Grinded into paste and drink in the morning in empty stomach.
83	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i> (L.) Benth. ex Kurz [Apocynaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 129 (HAU), 10.02.2022.	Kharwk	Roots	Allergy	Herb	Paste	Roots used are grinded into paste and put on the wound.
84	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L. [Euphorbiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 322 (HAU), 13.11.22	Indi bilai	Leaves	Allergy	Shrub	Paste	Leaves are grinded into paste and apply on the skin.
85	<i>Saccharum spontaneum</i> L. [Poaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 323 (HAU), 13.11.22	Roots	Roots	Jaundice	Shrub	Pieces	Roots facing east are cut into pieces and put inside the cocoon and wear it for 3-4 days.
86	<i>Scoparia dulchis</i> L. [Plantaginaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 130 (HAU), 23.11.2022	Bonfhang rakheb	Leaves	Stomach ache and Piles	Herb	Juice extract and Globules	1. Stomach ache: Leaves are grinded into paste juice extract is consumed for stomach ache. 2. Piles: Make a paste and tiny pills, sundry it for some time and consume after.
87	<i>Senna occidentalis</i> (L.) Link [Fabaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-011 (HAU), 10.02.2022,	Adidiga	Leaves	Stomach ache	Shrub	Extract	Leaves are grinded along with the rhizome of <i>Marantha arundinia</i> . The extract is then consumed during severe stomach ache.
88	<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm.f. [Malvaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 324 (HAU), 13.11.22	Bamwn nara	Leaves	Wound (Cancer like)	Herb	Paste	Leaves are grinded into paste and put on the wound.
89	<i>Shorea robusta</i> C.F.Gaertn. [Dipterocarpaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 325 (HAU), 13.11.22	Sal dongfang	Bark	Jaundice	Tree	Decoction	Bark is boiled and the decoction is used for taking bathe.
90	<i>Solanum torvum</i> Sw. [Solanaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 288 (HAU), 18.04.2024	Kunthai pisa	Roots	Jaundice	Shrub	Pieces	Roots facing east are cut into pieces and put inside the cocoon and wear it for 3-4 days.
91	<i>Solanum viarum</i> Dunal. [Solanaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 326 (HAU), 13.11.22	Bis kanthaokra	Fruits	Boil	Shrub	Paste	Fruits are grinded into paste and applied on the boil.
92	<i>Stellaria wallichiana</i> Haines [Caryophyllaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 087 (HAU), 17.03.2022.	Nabikhi	Whole plant	Mouth Ulcher and Jaundice	Herb	Steamed and paste	1. Mouth Ulcer: Whole plant is steamed along with a fish called na bwthia and applied on the ulcer. 2. Jaundice: Crushed into paste along with other ingredients and put on the head of the patient until it is cool down and sprinkle it with water whenever it dries.
93	<i>Stephania rotunda</i> Lour. [Menispermaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-015 (HAU), 21.05.2022.	Dumaolu bedor	Tuber	Gastric	Climber	Paste	Grinded into paste and soaked in the water for whole night and the extract is used.
94	<i>Strebilus asper</i> Lour. [Moraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 327 (HAU), 13.11.22	Sewra	Branch	Tooth Cavity	Tree	Piece	Small branch is used as a brush.
95	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (L.) Merr. & L.M.Perry [Myrtaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT014 (HAU), 20.04.2022	Laung	Seeds	Tooth Cavity and headache	Tree	Piece	1. Tooth Cavity: Seeds are insert in to tooth. 2. Headache: Ground with few ml of water into Paste and apply on the head for 5-6 hours.
96	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L. [Fabaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 091 (HAU), 24.02.2022	Thingkhling bilai	leaves	Aithing bainai	tree	paste	Ground into paste and the paste is applied on the broken part and wrapped and bind with the band aids for some days

97	<i>Tectona grandis</i> L.f. [Lamiaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 328 (HAU), 13.11.22	Sigun	Twig	Diarrhea	tree	paste	Twigs are boiled and patient is taken bath
98	<i>Tegetes erecta</i> L. [Asteraceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT- 329 (HAU), 13.11.22	narjee phool/Arba	flowers	Cuts and bleeding	herb	paste	Flowers are grinded and put on the cuts.
99	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wight & Arn. [Combretaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT-025 (HAU), 01.03.2022.	Arjun	Bark	Diabetes	tree	Decoction	Barks are boiled and the decoction is to drink
100	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb. [Combretaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 291 (HAU), 18.04.2024	Baora	Fruits	Gastric/Jaundice	Tree	Powder	Fruit is dried and ground into powder and can be consumed empty stomach.
101	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.; [Combretaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 292 (HAU), 18.04.2024	Selekha	Fruits	Gastric	Tree	Powder	Fruit is dried and ground into powder and can be consumed empty stomach.
102	<i>Thelypteris parasitica</i> (L.) Tardieu. [Aspleniaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 125 (HAU), 23.11.2022	Sal daokhumwi	Fronds	Allergy	Herb	Paste	Leaves are grinded into paste and the extract is to taken bath.
103	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe. [Zingiberaceae]; Kokrajhar JB & HT 300 (HAU), 27.04.2024	Haizeng	Tuber	Cough	Herb	Juice	Tuber along with leaves of <i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> and honey is use to drink to cure cough.
104	<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i> Mill. [Rahmnaceae]; Kokrajhar: JB & HT 215 (HAU); 06.11.2023	Bwigri bijou	Twigs and leaves	stomach ache	Tree	Paste and juice	Twigs and leaves are grounded and the juice extract is consumed for stomach ache.

References

- Abhijit D and De JN. 2010. Ethnoveterinary uses of Medicinal Plants by the Aborigines of Purulia District, West Bengal, India. *International Journal of Botany* 6: 433-440.
- Anyinam C. 1995. Ecology and ethnomedicine: Exploring links between the current environmental crisis and indigenous medical practices. *Social Science and Medicine* 40(3): 321– 329.
- Arora RK. 1987. Ethnobotany and its role in the conservation and use of the genetic resources in India. *Ethnobotany* 9: 6-15.
- Ashish MJ, Khadabadi SS, Farooqui IA and Ghorpade DS. 2010b. Studies on antimicrobial activity of *Clerodendrum infortunatum*, *Argyrea nervosa*, and *Vitex negundo*: A comparison. *Scholars Research Library, Der Pharmacia Lettre* 2(1): 102 – 105.
- Ashish MJ, Khadabadi SS and Deore S. 2010a. In vitro Anthelmintic Activity of *Clerodendrum infortunatum*: *International Journal of Pharm Tech Research* 2(1): 375 – 377.
- Basumatary T, Brahma P, Wary R, Bhuyan B and Baruah S. Ethnomedicinal study on roots and rhizomes used by the Bodo community of Kokrajhar district of Assam (India). *Pleione* 18(2): 159 – 166.
- Basumatary J, Abhaya AP, and Tag H. 2023. Plants used by the Bodo traditional community of Kokrajhar District (in BTAD) of Assam in Northeast India for the treatment of stomach disorders. *Pleione* 18(2): 214 – 227.
- Bhattacharjee D, Das A, Das SK and Chakraborty GS. 2011. *Clerodendrum infortunatum* Linn: A Review. *Journal of Advances in Pharmacy and Healthcare Research* 1(3): 82-8.
- Borthakur SK, Baro D, Bawri A and Boro A. 2018. *Flora of BTAD* (Bodoland Territorial Districts, Assam), Vol. 1-4. EBH Publishers, India.
- Borthakur SK. 1980. *Medicinal flora of Karbi-Anglong (Mikir-hills), Assam with reference to Ethnobotany*. Ph.D. Thesis submitted to Guahati University, Guwahati, Assam.
- Chandrika UG and Kumarab PAASP. 2015. Gotu Kola (*Centella asiatica*): Nutritional Properties and Plausible Health Benefits. In: *Advances in Food and Nutrition Research*, Vol. 76. Elsevier Inc. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/bs.afnr.2015.08.001>.
- Daimari M, Roy M K, Swargiary A, Baruah S and Basumatary S. 2019. An ethnobotanical survey of antidiabetic medicinal plants used by the Bodo tribe of Kokrajhar district. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge* 18 (3): 421 – 429.
- Das AP. 2021. Herbarium Techniques. In: J.B. Bhandari & Cyria Gurung (eds.), *Instrumentation Manual*. Narosa Publishing House, New Delhi. Pp. 78 – 94.
- Endle RS. 1911. *The Kacharis*. Akansha Publishing House, New Delhi, India.
- Gouthamchandra K, Mahmood R, Mohamed B, Khadeer A. Parameshwarappa SB and Venkatarangaiah K. 2009. Wound healing activity of *Clerodendrum infortunatum* Linn. Root extracts: *International Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 3(1): 21 – 25.
- Govaerts R. 2000. How many species of seed plants are there? *Taxon*. 50: 1085-1090.
- Hooker JD. 1872-1897. *Flora of British India*, Vols. 1-7. L. Reeve & Co Ltd, London.
- Jain SK and Rao RR. 1976. *A Handbook of Field and Herbarium Methods*. Today & Tomorrow's Printers and Publishers, New Delhi.
- Joseph B, George J, and Mohan J. 2013. Pharmacology and traditional uses of *Mimosa pudica*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research* 5(2): 41-44.
- Kanjilal U N, Das A, Kanjilal PC, Purkaystha C, De RN and Bor NL. 1934 – 1940. *Flora of Assam* (Vols. I – V). Government of Assam, Shillong [Printed by: Prabasi Press, Calcutta].
- Kirtikar RB and Basu BD. 1935. *Indian Medicinal Plants*, Vols. I - IV. Lalit Mohan Basu, Allahabad.
- Martin G.J. 1995. *Ethnobotany: A Methods Manual*. 1st ed. New York, Chapman & Hall, London. Pp. 1-64.
- Modi AJ, Khadabadi SS, Deore SL and Kubde MS. 2010. Antioxidant effects of leaf of *Clerodendrum infortunatum* (Linn.). *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research* 1(4): 67 – 72.
- Pattanayak P, Behera P, Das D, and Panda S K. 2010. *Ocimum sanctum* Linn. A reservoir plant for therapeutic applications: An overview. *Pharmacognosy Reviews* 4(7): 95.
- Phillips O, Gentry AH, Reynel C, Wilkin P and Galvez-Durand BC. 1994. Quantitative ethnobotany and amazonian conservation: conservation etnobotánica cuantitativa y la conservación de la amazonia. *Conservation Biology* 8: 225–248.
- Prain D. 1903. *Bengal Plants*. Vols. I & II. West, Newman & Co., London.
- POWO. 2023. Plants of the world online. <https://powo.science.kew.org/> Trustee Royal Botanic Garden, Kew UK.
- Pushpagandan P. 1995. Ethnopharmacology of *Trichopus zeylanicus*- The ginseng of Kerala- A review. In: P. Pushpagandan, Uff Nyman and V George (Eds.), *Proceeding of the first National Conference on Ethnopharmacology*. Visual Security Printing Enterprises Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi (India).
- Pushpagandan P. 1996. *Ethnobiology in India: A status report*. Govt. of India, New Delhi.
- Santanu S, Mazumder UK, Dilipkumar P and Silpi M. 2009. Lipid Hepatoprotective potential of methanol extract of *Clerodendrum infortunatum* Linn. against CCl₄ induced hepatotoxicity in rats. *Pharmacognosy Magazine* 5(20): 394 – 399.
- Sarmah P, Neog M, Bhuyan M K, and Basumatary P. 2021. Ethnomedicinal plants and their traditional use for treatment of diabetes in Kokrajhar district of Assam. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 10 (01): 464-477.
- Schipmann U, Leaman DJ, Cunningham AB. 2002. Impact of cultivation and gathering of medicinal plants on biodiversity: Global trends and issues. In: FAO (eds.) *Biodiversity and ecosystem approach in agriculture, forestry and fishery*. Satellite event on the occasion of the ninth regular session and commission on genetic resources for food and agriculture, Rome.
- Solecki R and Shanidar IV. 1975. A Neanderthal flower burial in northern Iraq. *Science* 190: 880-881.
- Swargiary A, Daimari M and Roy M K. 2021. Putative anthelmintic plants used in traditional medicine system of Kokrajhar district, India. *Ethnobotany Research and Applications* 22: 1-18.
- Tag H, Kalita P, Dwivedi P, Das AK, Nima DN. 2012. Herbal medicines used in the treatment of diabetes mellitus in Arunachal Himalaya, northeast, India. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 141 (3): 786 – 795.
- Tag H. 2007. *A systematic study of plants of ethnomedicinal importance used by the Khamti tribe of Arunachal Pradesh*. Submitted to Rajiv Gandhi University for Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Botany (unpublished).
- Yakang B, Gajurel PR, Potsangbam S and Bhuyan LR. 2013. Account of common and traditional non-timber forest products used by Apatani tribe of Arunachal Pradesh, India. *Pleione* 7 (2): 514 - 529.

